

VERSAL AI ENGINES FOR ON-BOARD DATA COMPRESSION: IMPLEMENTATION AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF CCSDS 121 AND CCSDS 123

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ABSTRACT

The rapid increase in data generated by Earth observation and deep-space missions, coupled with the limited capacity of downlink channels, has made data compression a crucial task in Payload Data Handling Units. This paper evaluates an efficient implementation of the CCSDS 121.0-B-3 and CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compression algorithms on the AMD Versal Adaptive Intelligent Engines. Both compression standards, designed for general data and hyperspectral image compression, are mapped to the Versal's many-core architecture to assess performance in terms of data throughput and resource efficiency. Targeting the Versal AI Cores series, the algorithms are adapted to vectorized processing in a pipelined manner. The results demonstrate that the AI Engines can achieve high throughput, with both compression algorithms reaching up to 8.8 Gbit/s while utilizing only half of the AI Engine array. Challenges encountered during the implementation, including vectorization, memory constraints, and dependency management within the CCSDS 123 algorithm, are analyzed and discussed. Although the AI Engines demonstrate a strong performance for certain tasks, the results indicate that further improvements could be achieved by combining the AI Engines with Programmable Logic.

INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in space technology have significantly increased the amount of data generated by Earth observation and deep-space missions, initiating a shift towards direct on-board data processing instead of post-processing on Earth. Further driven by limited downlink capabilities, there is a growing need for advanced data processing systems capable of performing complex calculations and compression tasks to enhance efficiency and responsiveness. The Versal Advanced Compute Acceleration Platform (ACAP) aims to address this need by providing a many-core architecture called Adaptive Intelligent (AI) Engines, designed for parallelizable high-speed computational tasks and handling large data volumes. This paper focuses on evaluating the performance of essential PDHU tasks mapped onto the Versal AI Engines. Specifically, the CCSDS 121.0-B-3 (CCSDS 121) and the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 (CCSDS 123) compression algorithms are adapted and implemented to determine the feasibility and effectiveness of mapping them onto the many-core architecture of the Versal AI Engines.

The overall project setup presented in this paper is intentionally simplified to focus on determining the performance of the CCSDS 121 and CCSDS 123 mapped onto the Versal AI Engines. From the satellite's subsystems, only the Payload Data Handling Unit is considered, with the AMD Versal AI Core VC1902 as the main processing unit. Hardware evaluation is conducted using the AMD VCK190 development board. For compression, data is transferred sample-by-sample from DDR memory through the Programmable Logic (PL) to the AI Engines.

BACKGROUND ON CCSDS COMPRESSION

The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) has developed a series of standards for lossless and lossy data compression. Two of these standards, CCSDS 121 and CCSDS 123, which are widely used in current and next-generation Earth observation missions, are implemented for evaluation on the Versal AI Engines.

CCSDS 121 Compression

The CCSDS 121 standard provides a flexible framework for compressing a wide range of digital data and is defined at the algorithmic level [1]. The CCSDS 121 algorithm consists of two stages, a preprocessor and an adaptive entropy coder stage, as shown in Fig.1. The input data, processed sample-by-sample, can be either signed or unsigned integers with a

Fig. 1. CCSDS 121 algorithm block diagram. Image by [1], adopted by authors

bit depth of up to 32 bits. The preprocessor reduces data correlation by predicting the next incoming value based on the previous sample. The prediction error is calculated and mapped to non-negative integers. The entropy coder stage processes a block of J consecutive preprocessed samples and applies Rice's adaptive coding technique to generate a variable-length codeword. Several coding options are evaluated concurrently, and the option resulting in the shortest coded data set (CDS) is selected for compression.

CCSDS 123 Compression

The CCSDS 123 standard is designed for compressing multi- or hyperspectral images in a lossless or near-lossless manner [2]. A multi- or hyperspectral image can be represented as a three-dimensional array with integer values of up to 32 bits. The compression is performed sequentially in a single pass through the image, where each sample corresponds to a pixel denoted as $s_z(t) \equiv s_{z,y,x}$ using spatial indices x and y and the spectral band index z .

The CCSDS 123 algorithm consists of two stages, as shown in Fig. 2. The predictor stage is based on a closed-loop scheme and uses an adaptive, weighted linear prediction method. The stage predicts the value of each pixel based on the values of the neighbouring pixels within a small three-dimensional neighbourhood. The difference between the prediction and the actual sample is quantized and mapped to non-negative integers for actual compression by the encoder stage. The predictor can be configured in several modes to determine which pixels and spectral bands are used for prediction. To achieve lossless compression, the quantizer step can be omitted.

The second stage, the encoder stage, offers three encoder types for the actual compression. The sample-adaptive entropy coding and the hybrid coding approaches evaluate each sample individually, while the block-adaptive entropy coder compresses multiple samples at once.

VERSAL AI ENGINES

The Versal ACAP comprises a heterogeneous compute architecture combining three hardware concepts in a single chip: Programmable Logic, two dual-core ARM processors, and an AI Engine array [3]. Among the Versal devices, two configurations (XQRVC1902 and XQRVE2302) are available in a space-grade version to the authors knowledge.

The AI Engine array consists of 400 AI Engine tiles, with each tile housing an AI Engine and a 32 KB data memory. Each Engine consists of a Very Long Instruction Word (VLIW) based processor consisting of a 32-bit scalar RISC unit and two vector units, all operating at 1.0 GHz. The vector units are capable of Single Instruction, Multiple Data (SIMD) operations, making the AI Engines well-suited for vector-based calculations. Each AI Engine can access the data memory

Fig. 2. CCSDS 123 algorithm block diagram. Image by [2], adopted by authors

in its neighboring tiles and data can also be transferred through an AXI4 stream and a cascade stream. The AI Engines are programmed in the Vitis IDE through a C/C++ application called kernel, while interfaces and data movements are defined in a graph-based programming model.

The VLIW microcode is loaded from the program memory and executed on the scalar and vector units. The vector units, utilizing SIMD operations, can execute an instruction across multiple elements of a vector simultaneously. As a result, they can perform up to 128 8-bit MAC operations in a single clock cycle. In contrast, the scalar unit requires three clock cycles for multiplication and one clock cycle for addition on a single sample. The AI Engines' vector units are a key asset, and algorithm mapping should prioritize vector-based operations to maximize performance.

GENERAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Implementing the CCSDS 121 and CCSDS 123 algorithms on the Versal AI Engines requires a fundamentally new approach, particularly given the many-core architecture of this hardware platform. For the implementation presented in this paper, a pipelining approach was selected adapt the algorithms. The CCSDS compression algorithms rely on sequential data processing, which makes them well-suited for pipelined execution. This method not only optimizes resource usage but also ensures continuous data processing and a structured implementation through partitioning. The algorithms are divided into smaller functional blocks, each of which can be mapped to an individual AI Engine. Each engine performs its designated operation and then passes the data to the next engine in the pipeline. However, the overall performance is constrained by the slowest engine in the pipeline. Therefore, the implementation must aim for balanced execution times across all engines, ensuring that each engine processes its data block within approximately the same number of cycles. Additionally, it is essential to implement the processing steps using vector-based operations. This ensures that the AI Engines can take full advantage of their SIMD capabilities, further optimizing performance.

CCSDS 121 IMPLEMENTATION

The CCSDS 121 compression algorithm processes data samples sequentially, except in the encoding stage where full blocks are processed. Block-based calculations are exploited to realize vector-based processing. A block of data with J samples is mapped to a single vector in the AI Engine. This is extended across the entire compression chain to leverage vectorized processing. However, the AI Engine vector registers are limited in size, ranging from 128 to 1024 bits. This introduces constraints on the number of samples per block (J) that can be stored in a vector, as the product of J and the bit width per sample is required to be within a range of 128-bit to 1024-bit. Additionally, the AI Engines are not supporting unsigned INT16 and unsigned INT32, so signed datatypes must be used with the sign as overhead.

The resulting pipelined architecture for the Versal AI Engines contains three subgraphs. Two of them are corresponding to the algorithmic processing stages and the third one is used to encode data into the coded data sets (CDS), since this process is computationally expensive and complex. Fig. 3 is showing the resulting graph, containing the three subgraphs in light blue. The boxes in the subgraphs are representing a kernel, hence a C application targeting one AI Engine. The color of the box indicates whether the function is vector-based or not. The arrows between the Engines are a simplified view on the data movement between the kernels.

Fig. 3. CCSDS 121 AI Engines implementation graph, where each box represents a processing kernel. The color coding differentiates between vector-based and scalar-based processing.

The preprocessor stage is fully vectorized and pipelined, as the operations are independent and can be processed in parallel across the vector lanes. In the entropy coder stage, certain optimizations were made to reduce processing load, such as determining the best split-sample option based on the mean of the data vector rather than evaluating all possible options. At the output of the second stage, the determined compression option for the current block is available. Although vector-based processing is used extensively in the first two stages, the third stage, which generates the CDS, cannot be vectorized. To avoid bottlenecking the system, this stage employs four parallel CDS generation lanes, each consisting of 16 kernels. All data transfers between kernels, except for control signals, are using vector-based communication to maximize efficiency. While the processing flow is linear, the AI Engines operate in parallel, ensuring that each engine processes data concurrently and forwards it to the next engine at the end of each iteration.

CCSDS 123 IMPLEMENTATION

Implementing the CCSDS 123 algorithm on the Versal AI Engines presents several challenges due to the complexity of the predictor stage and the dependencies between consecutive predictions. Adapting the algorithm for vectorized processing requires careful consideration of these dependencies and the realizable design options.

In this implementation, a lossless compression configuration is selected, with the wide column-oriented mode chosen for the local sum due to its suitability for efficient pipelining. Additionally, the reduced prediction mode is applied for the same reason. Table 1 summarizes the configuration and selected parameters for this implementation.

The vectorization of the CCSDS 123 algorithm is heavily influenced by the choice of data ordering. The calculation of the new weights $w(t + 1)$ depends directly on the prediction residual $\Delta_z(t)$ of the pixel $s(t)$. Therefore, to process multiple samples in a single vector, the samples must not be consecutive in t but instead need to come from separate spectral bands. The only ordering that satisfies this requirement is the Band Interleaved by Pixel (BIP) ordering.

Using the BIP ordering results in an increase in memory requirements, as all spectral bands for a pixel must be processed before moving to the next pixel. For datasets by imagers such as AVIRIS [4], the memory required exceeds the available storage within a single AI Engine tile. While external memory (e.g., DDR) could be used, the goal of this implementation is to run exclusively on the AI Engines. Dividing the image into sub-images can reduce the memory needs, however, segmentation along the x- and y-axes does not work well with BIP ordering. Segmentation along the z-axis (across spectral bands) is more suitable for pipelining, although this approach introduces additional memory requirements to store previous spectral bands. Given these constraints, for the presented implementation no segmentation is applied and the data storage load is distributed across multiple AI Engines to manage the memory demands. A distribution unit ensures that samples are routed to the appropriate AI Engine, so data dependencies are managed. In addition to calculating the local sum, the same engines also compute central local differences. The central local difference vector is consisting of multiple vectors and combined with the corresponding weight vectors. The resulting prediction residual is needed to update the weight vector in the weight vector kernel. Since this kernel provides the weights for the calculation of the next predicted central local difference, this creates a critical path. The predicted central local difference kernel needs to wait for new weights until the prediction of the preceding pixel has been processed. To optimize processing time of this critical path, all processing is combined into a single kernel to minimize transmission overhead.

As encoder, a block-adaptive coding configuration is used, following the recommendations of the standard. Both encoder stages developed for the CCSDS 121 are completely reused. The full CCSDS 123 graph is shown in Fig. 4.

IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

The CCSDS 121 and CCSDS 123 applications implemented on the Versal AI Engines were tested and validated using different input data sets. For validation, a golden reference is generated in parallel by the ESA Whitedwarf [5] and the CNES compression tools [6]. Both hardware simulation and testing on the evaluation board provide cycle accurate execution time measurements. For both implementations, the pipelined throughput is based on the kernel having largest execution time.

Table 1. CCSDS 123 configuration

Compression mode	Lossless
Prediction mode	Reduced
Local Sum	Wide column oriented
Sample Representatives	Not used, $s''(t) = s(t)$
Pixel Order	BIP
Encoder	Block adaptive entropy (CCSDS121)

Fig. 4. CCSDS 123 AI Engines implementation graph where each box represents a processing kernel. The color coding differentiates between vector-based and scalar-based processing.

For the CCSDS 121, despite significant efforts to balance workload, it is not entirely possible due to the CDS packing on the scalar units. To evaluate the effect of this stage on the other stages, all stages have been tested individually. As input, 7-bit and 31-bit samples, stored in INT8 and INT32, have been used. The results are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that the data encoder stage is indeed still significantly slowing down the other stages.

For the full evaluation, two data sets are tested and the results revealed in Table 3. The average test sequence triggers each compression option once. The worst-case sequence triggers only the slowest coding option to provide a minimum data rate. The resources needed are summarized in Table 6 left. Of the 400 AI Engines, 45 percent are used for the presented implementation. Most of them are occupied by the data encoder stage.

For the CCSDS 123 compression implementation, the performance depends on the image size in the z-dimension. Table 4 presents the throughput of the predictor stage for a different number of spectral bands.

The complete CCSDS 123 compression speed results are shown in Table 5. For the 7- and 31-bit data samples, random test data has been used. For the 15-bit design, 16-bit AVIRIS-classic data samples [4] were selected. All samples in the data set fit naturally in 15-bit, so no clipping was needed. For all tests, 224 spatial bands were used. The resources needed for the CCSDS 123 implementation are shown in Table 6 right.

In regard to power, the Versal is seen as a challenging component due to its potential high-power consumption. The AI Engines are additionally sharing a power island with the PL, which makes general power estimations and measurements more complicated. For the CCSDS 121, the power is estimated to be 18 W dynamic and 5 W static (Tool: Power Estimator, Versal AI Core XCVC1902, Package: VSVA2197, Junction Temp: 25 degree C). For the CCSDS 123 implementation, the dynamic power consumption is at 22 W and 5 W static power.

IMPLEMENTATION EVALUATION

For evaluating compression algorithms, real missions and imagers can be used to determine if the achieved performance is suitable for modern systems. The Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for Environment (CHIME) is a future mission by ESA providing hyperspectral Earth observations. The mission shall achieve input data rates up to 2 Gbps [7]. The AI Engine implementations presented in this paper - CCSDS 121 and CCSDS 123 - achieve up to 8.8 Gbit/s compression throughput and therefore significantly exceed this target.

Table 2. CCSDS 121 intermediate speeds

Input	Preprocessor	Adaptive Entropy Coder	Data Encoder
7 Bit	7 Gbit/s	7 Gbit/s	4,1 Gbit/s
31 Bit	18,9 Gbit/s	18,9 Gbit/s	8,8 Gbit/s

Table 3. CCSDS 121 compression throughput

Input	Average Test sequence	Worst Case Test sequence
7 Bit	4.1 Gb/s (580 Msamples/s)	3.6 Gb/s (510 Msamples/s)
15 Bit	7.2 Gb/s (480 Msamples/s)	6.8 Gb/s (450 Msamples/s)
31 Bit	8.8 Gb/s (283 Msamples/s)	7.8 Gb/s (251 Msamples/s)

Table 4. CCSDS 123 predictor speed for different numbers of spectral bands

Number of spectral bands Nz	Vectors	Throughput
64	1	423 Msamples/s
128	2	576 Msamples/s
256	3	750 Msamples/s
512	4	369 Msamples/s

Table 5. CCSDS 123 compression throughput

Input bit width	Dataset	Throughput
7 bit	Random	3.9 Gb/s (557 Msamples/s)
15 bit	AVIRIS classic	7.2 Gb/s (476 Msamples/s)
31 bit	Random	8.7 Gb/s (279 Msamples/s)

The data rates obtained for the CCSDS 121 confirm the potential of the vector-based processing. All functions implemented using the vector units demonstrate high performance, while the data encoder stage, which operates on scalar units, performs significantly slower despite consuming nearly 80% of the used resources. This disparity illustrates the performance differences between vector-based and scalar-based operations on the Versal AI Engines.

For 16-bit, the CCSDS 121 AI Engine implementation (with 15-bit input samples) is competitive, as shown in Fig. 5. It outperforms the FPGA-based SHyLoC core [8], but does not quite reach the performance of a highly pipelined FPGA implementation [10]. However, for larger input samples, the AI Engines 31-bit implementation surpasses all other hardware, including CPU, GPU, and FPGA implementations. Notably, increasing the sample size from 16 to 32 bits typically doubles the resource requirements on FPGAs and reduces throughput [9]. This issue is far less severe for the AI Engines, and this flexibility in handling various data types gives the AI Engine a distinct advantage over FPGA implementations, especially for data sizes larger than 16 bits.

For the CCSDS 123 AI Engine implementation, the predictor stage performs well but is hindered by the CCSDS 121-based encoder. The graph in Figure 6 compares the full CCSDS 123 compression performance to several studies and implementations. For 16-bit samples, most studies also used AVIRIS datasets. The AI Engine implementation performs competitively but is outpaced clearly by a few recent high-performance FPGA designs. These designs are often based on a parallelized structure with multiple compression engines. The single performance of an engine by [12], for example, performs at 4.56 Gb/s, and achieves more speed through parallelism. For data sizes greater than 16 bits, the AI Engines once again demonstrate unmatched performance. Most existing implementations, including the VHDL-based ones, are optimized for 16-bit data. Only the FPGA-based SHyLoC IP core [8] reported results for 32-bit samples. However, it is important to note that the SHyLoC is highly versatile and supports all possible configurations while the AI Engine implementation presented in this paper is currently limited and optimized to a few modes.

In terms of power, both AI Engine implementations achieve around 18 Msamples/s/W and are therefore more efficient than GPU based solutions achieving around 5 Msamples/s/W. However, the power efficiency of most FPGA implementations achieving up to hundreds of Msamples/s/W cannot be reached.

SUMMARY

The evaluation of the CCSDS 121 and CCSDS 123 compression algorithms on the Versal AI Engines has demonstrated the potential of this many-core architecture for high-throughput data processing tasks in space missions. The CCSDS 121 implementation achieved data rates of up to 8.8 Gbit/s, utilizing only half of the available AI Engine resources. Similarly, the CCSDS 123 implementation, while more complex due to the predictor stage and memory challenges, achieved 7.2 Gbit/s on the hyperspectral AVIRIS datasets.

Table 6. CCSDS 121 (left) and CCSDS 123 (right) AI Engines resources

Stage	Number of tiles	Number of kernels	Stage	Number of tiles	Number of kernels
Preprocessor	15	9	Predictor	33	27
Adaptive Entropy Coder	28	21	Adaptive Entropy Coder (CCSDS 121)	28	21
Data Encoder	137	86	Data Encoder (CCSDS 121)	137	86
Full CCSDS 121	180	116	Full CCSDS 123	198	134

Fig. 5. CCSDS 121 Throughput Comparison

Fig. 6. CCSDS 123 Throughput Comparison

This paper highlights the importance of vector-based processing for optimizing the performance of the AI Engines. The effectiveness of the AI Engine architecture relies heavily on careful adaptation of the algorithms to the vector units and efficient management of data flow through pipelined processing.

Moreover, certain stages, particularly those that rely on scalar processing, continue to be bottlenecks, indicating that further optimization is needed.

Looking ahead, future work should explore hybrid implementations that combine the strengths of the AI Engines with programmable logic (PL) to further enhance performance and efficiency. This hybrid approach could mitigate some of the memory and computational challenges faced in purely AI Engine-based implementations, particularly for complex, multi-stage algorithms like CCSDS 123. Additionally, optimizing for power efficiency remains a key focus, as energy consumption is critical for space missions.

In conclusion, while the Versal AI Engines show significant promise for on-board data handling tasks, particularly in terms of throughput, the best results may be achieved by strategically integrating AI Engines with other components of the Versal architecture. This combination will provide a more flexible, scalable solution for future space missions, capable of handling diverse computational workloads with greater efficiency.

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